

Validity and Reliability of Survey Scales

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to evaluate Likert and non-Likert scales for quantitative survey. The data used in the evaluation of the scale is the scale components. The scales used for the evaluation include the following types: (0,1,2,3), (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10). These scales are categorized into two types, namely Likert and non-Likert. The scale (0,1,2,3) is classified as non-Likert; the remaining scales are Likert scales. The efficacy of various scales is evaluated on the basis of fitness. We defined fitness as the ratio between shape and scale of the scaled obtained through the QQ plot linear equation. We found that scale (0,1,2,3) is the most effective scale type for quantitative response choice. The efficacy of the scale was measured by the absolute error of the scale's fitness CDF. The absolute error of the CDF of the fitness were 0.14, 0.22, 0.25 and 0.26 for the following types: (0,1,2,3), (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10), respectively. The results of GOF under the likelihood ratio test, Wald statistic and Lagrangian multiplier shows that the non-Likert scale (0,1,2,3) has the best fit in the probability space of the unit circle: 0.71, 0.68, and 0.70, respectively. Response in a form of (0,1,2,3) is the best form of response scale for quantitative survey. This finding is a contribution to the field because the common use of the Likert scale has made findings and conclusion in many cases in social science research lacking validity due to low accuracy.

Keywords: Gautama scale, instrument calibration, Likert scale, Monte Carlo, non-Likert scale, reliability, validity

JEL Code: C80, C82, C89

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Likert Scale and its usage

This paper is motivated by the needs to look for response scale that is a better alternative to the Likert scale. The Likert scale is commonly used in social science research. Despite its convenience and common usage, the Likert scale is not an accurate tool to gauge respondent's opinion on a sequential scale. This problem is blinded by the fact that when researchers seek to explain the "reliability", the most commonly measure is Cronbach's alpha. This paper points out that Cronbach's alpha is not a proper measure for instrument evaluation. A key to evaluate the instrument, i.e. survey, is the measure of accuracy of the response scale.

Research in social science commonly employed written survey as an instrument to collect data. In quantitative survey, the survey may employ one of any number of response scale types. These scale types include: (0,1,2,3), (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10). The scale in a form of (0,1,2,3) may be called non-Likert scale. These scales: (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10), may be called Likert scales. This paper evaluates the validity or accuracy of the Likert and non-Likert scales in quantitative survey.

Likert scale was introduced by Rensis Likert in 1932 (Likert, 1992). It is commonly used for collecting response data in social science research. The scale may be in any of the following forms: (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), or (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10). There are two defects in these scales. First, the scale does not contain zero. The absence of zero limits data analysis to only continuous distribution for purposes of hypothesis testing. Secondly, by using 1 as the lowest value, the scale produces an artificial "lowest" value. The value 1 in any of the Likert scale form does not represent the "true lowest" value. Thirdly, the all Likert scale forms produce artificially higher mean; therefore, inflates the mean and, thus, creates greater potential for Type I error. In light of these weaknesses of the Likert scale, the non-Likert scale (0,1,2,3) may present a more logical alternative.

One critique of the Likert scale is that it is used as non-numerical or non-quantitative, linear modeling may not be appropriate tool for analysis (Knapp, 1990). Respondents may also cause confusion of whether the choices between components of Likert scale have equi-distance (Dawes, 2008). In a case where the Likert scale is descriptive, it must be converted to number scale before it could be analyzed (Kuzon et al., 1996). For Likert supports, in order to make the scale reliable, it must contain at least six items (Carifer, 2008; Carifero, 2007). Some claimed that the Likert 5 and 7 item scales are reliable (Vicker, 1999). However, this claim is not convincing. Vickers' study on responses to reported that the Likert-type single question of pain yielded a higher mean value than the same question posed to the same group using a Visual Analog Scale; Vickers concluded that the Likert-type response was "a more responsive measure." This is a misinterpretation of the finding. The evidence shows precisely the problem of the Likert scale; it creates an artificially inflated mean. This inflated mean is created by non-zero minimum and the inflation intensifies with more choices. For example, 5-points scale (1,2,3,4,5) has a mean of 3 and the 7-points scale has a mean of 4. Therefore, we treat Vickers' conclusion as Type 2 error. Type 2 error occurs when the null hypothesis is falsely rejected (Shermer, 2002). The Likert scale produces artificially high mean, thus, gives a pretense of proving the hypothesis and rejects the null hypothesis. This is a false proof because the Likert scale produces a false mean. In light of the inefficiency of the Likert scale and other developments in survey response (Reips and Funke, 2008), we urge using other alternatives that are more reliable than the Likert scale. In this paper, we present (0,1,2,3) as an alternative scale.

1.2 Non-Likert scale as better alternative

The non-Likert quantitative scale in a form of (0,1,2,3) was introduced by Gautama Buddha 2600 years ago. This Buddhist scale categorizes levels of all things into two category; things that is extinguished is called zero (*sunyatha*), and things that persists may be measured in three levels, namely low (1: *pathama*), medium (2: *machima*) and high (3: *paramatra*). Any written works on

quantitative scale in a form of (0,1,2,3) subsequent to Gautama Buddha were only the re-discovery of older works in Buddhism.

The Gautama scale (0,1,2,3) contains zero. This allows respondents to give the true value for “lowest” level of the response; as the result, the mean is not artificially inflated. The zero and non-zero components of the (0,1,2,3) scale, allows the researcher to engage in both discrete and continuous probabilities as tools for hypothesis testing.

It is a common mistake to report alpha Cronbach as the indicator of reliability or validity. The Cronbach alpha cannot verify the reliability or validity of the instrument. The Cronbach alpha measures the consistency of responses in a set of survey. This is a measurement of responses; it does not measure the efficacy of the instrument itself. If the survey is defective for lack of accuracy, no matter how high the Cronbach alpha may be, a defective instrument remains defective. Consistency of responses represents no more than consistent result of defective instrument. Cronbach wrote that: “I no longer regard the alpha formula as the most appropriate way to examine most data. Over the years, my associate and I developed the complex generalizability (G) theory.” Cronbach *et al.* (1963, 1973).

In this paper, our evaluation of the response scale is the tool to verify whether the instrument is valid. The function of validity test is to verify the accuracy of the response. What good can the consistency of responses do when the instrument itself is not accurate?

Accuracy is defined as precision. Precision is minimal error between the observed and expected values. The expected value is defined as the center of probability space in the unit circle where the cumulative distribution function (CDF) is at 0.50 or 50% point. A valid instrument is defined as one that produces responses or potential responses that lie closest to the center of the center of the unit circle of the probability space or $CDF = 0$.

The purpose of this paper is to verify that among these types of response scale, which scale is the most accurate: (0,1,2,3), (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10) ? Accuracy is defined as zero or minimal error between the CDF of the fitness of the responses produced by each scale compared to the ideal location at $CDF^* = 0$.

This paper asks: “which type of response scale is more accurate and reliable?” Accuracy is the indication of validity. Response scale in survey that is not accurate would fail the test of validity of the instrument. Reliability is the test for consistency. However, consistency must be read with validity in order to avoid false reading of the scale.

2.0 LITERATURE

Opinion survey involves psychological measurement called psychometrics. They are commonly used in social science research, particularly psychology and education (Kaplan and Sacuzzo, 2010). The measurement may employ survey that requires respondents to give answer in multiple choice of scale or dichotomous answer of yes or no (Andrich and Lou, 1993). There are three theoretical approaches that laid the foundation for psychometrics, namely *Classical Test Theory*, *Item-Response Theory* (Emberetson and Reise, 2000; Hambleton and Swaminathan, 1985), and the Rasch model (Rasch, 1960/1980).

Firstly, the Classical Test Theory (CTT) asserts that the observed score is a sum of the true score and error score. the aim of CTT is to understand and improve psychological testing method. The goal of CTT is to obtain the index of reliability in the response space. CTT depends on three components: observed test score (X), true variance of the test score (σ_T^2), and variance of the observed error of the test score (σ_x^2), the reliability ratio is given:

$$\rho_{xT}^2 = \frac{\sigma_T^2}{\sigma_x^2} \quad (1)$$

which may equivalently be written as:

$$\rho_{xT}^2 = \frac{\sigma_T^2}{\sigma_x^2} = \frac{\sigma_T^2}{\sigma_T^2 + \sigma_E^2} \quad (2)$$

The expression in (1) and (2) are called signal-to-noise ratio. In the context of reliability of responses of test score, reliability is high when the variance of error is low.

The reliability sought under CTT is obtained through the result of the responses, not the instrument used to obtain the responses (Pui-Wei and Wu, 2007). CTT relies heavily on correlation coefficient among response items. This is a point that this paper diverge; we are seeking the means to determine the reliability of the instrument, not the reliability of the response (Hambleton *et al.*, 1991).

The second theoretical approach to psychometrics is Item Response Theory (IRT). In IRT, questions do not have the same level of difficulty. For instance, in a Likert scale response space, each item is treated with the same level of difficulty; thus, the Likert scale is called parallel instrument (Van Alphen *et al.*, 1994). In IRT, treats the difficulty of each item as a separate score that needs to be examined in context of the entire test items (Ostini *et al.*, 2005; Nering and Reise, 2000). Thus, it is seen as a better approach in comparison to CTT (Embretson *et al.*, 2000).

The robustness of IRT is attested in its approach to provide a verifiable modeling of reliability of the test score. The modeling approach under IRT comes in two forms: three-parameter logistic model (3PL) and two parameters logistic model (2PL). The 3PL is presented by:

$$p_i(\theta) = c_i + \frac{1 - c_i}{1 + e^{-a_i(\theta - b_i)}} \quad (3)$$

where θ = person's ability which may be modeled from normal distribution; a = discrimination, scale, slope where the maximum slope is $p'(b) = a \cdot (1 - c) / 4$, b = level of difficulty, item location: $p(b) = (1 + c) / 2$, the half-way point between c_i (min) and 1(max) where the slope is maximized; and c = pseudo-guessing, chance, asymptotic minimum $p(-\infty) = c$.

The 2PL model assumes that there is no guessing (Thissen and Orlando, 2001). However, the items could vary in location (b_i) and discrimination (a_i). The 2PL approach is called normal-ogive model. The 2PL model is given by:

$$p_i(\theta) = \Phi\left(\frac{\theta - b_i}{\sigma_i}\right) \quad (4)$$

where Φ = cumulative distribution function (CDF) of a standard normal distribution curve, b_i = level of difficulty, and σ_i = discrimination. The standard deviation of the measurement error for item i is equal to $1/a_i$.

The third approach to psychometric test is called the Rasch model (Rasch, 1960/1980). The Rasch model has been used in marketing research (Bechtel, 1985). The Rasch model has general applicability in many fields in social science (Wright, 1977). Rasch model is similar to IRT (Linacre, 2005). Rasch claimed that unlike IRT, the Rasch model can accommodate specific objectivity (Rasch 1977). There are three types of Rasch models; each model depends on the type of data.

The first type of Rasch model deals with dichotomous data. Dichotomous data are binary. Binary data are those that had been generated by questions soliciting "yes" or "no" response. The

“yes” is scored as 1 and “no” is scored 0. The probability of the expected outcome for the Rasch model for dichotomous model is given by:

$$\Pr\{X_{ni} = 1\} = \frac{e^{\beta_n - \delta_i}}{1 + e^{\beta_n - \delta_i}} \quad (5)$$

where β_n = person’s ability, σ_i = level of difficulty of item i , $\Pr\{X_{ni} = 1\}$ = probability of success upon interaction of person and the assessment test, $\beta_n - \delta_i$ = correct responses; and δ_i = difficulty.

The second type of Rasch model deals with polytomous data. Polytomous data are defined as non-binary data where the answer choices consists of a range of values, for instance score of (0,1,2,3) as response choice. In polytomous case, the Rasch model is explained the partial credit model where $X_{ni} = x \in \{0,1,\dots,m_i\}$ is integer of random variable where m_i is the maximum score of item i . The term X_{mi} is random variable that can take value from 0 to m_i . The probability of the outcome $X_{ni} = x$ is explained by Master (Master, 1982) as:

$$\Pr\{X_{ni} = x, x > 0\} = \frac{\exp \sum_{k=1}^x (\beta_n - \tau_{ki})}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m_i} \exp \sum_{k=1}^j (\beta_n - \tau_{ki})} \quad (6)$$

$$\Pr\{X_{ni} = 0\} = \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^{m_i} \exp(\beta_n - \tau_{ki})} \quad (7)$$

where τ_{ki} is the k^{th} threshold of item i , β_n = location of person n on same continuum, m_i = maximum score for item i . The partial credit model could be rewritten as:

$$\Pr\{X_{ni} = x\} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^x (\beta_n - \tau_{ki})}{\sum_{j=0}^{m_i} \exp(\beta_n - \tau_{ki})} \quad (8)$$

where τ_{0i} is selected for convenience in computation: $\sum_{k=0}^{m_i} (\beta_n - \tau_{ki}) = 0$.

The third Rasch model is called the rating scale model (Andrich, 1978). The model is given by:

$$\Pr = \{X_{ni} = x\} = \frac{\exp \sum_{k=0}^x (\beta_n - (\delta_i - \tau_k))}{\sum_{j=0}^m \exp(\beta_n - (\delta_i - \tau_k))} \quad (9)$$

where δ_i = difficulty of item i , $\tau_k = k^{th}$ threshold of the rating scale common to all items, and τ_0 is chosen for computational convenience.

The three psychometric methods: CTT, IRT and Rasch models are tools for evaluating the outcome of the survey. They are not tools to evaluate the reliability of the survey or instrument used to collect the data. Therefore, existing literature on psychometrics has room to further contribution. This paper intends to examine the reliability of the survey, not the consistency or reliability of the responses to the survey.

2.1 Validity of an instrument

Validity test is a test of precision between the observed and the expected observation (Brains and Manhein, 2011). Traditionally, validity test in the literature is concerned with experimental design, not instrumental design (Cronbach and Meehl, 1955). When discussing experimental designs, the following sub-issues of validity are discussed: construct validity (Cronbach and Meehl, 1955); content validity (Pennington, 2003; Guion, 1980); face validity (Holden, 2010; Gravetter *et al.*, 2012);

criterion validity (Satu *et al.*, 2017); concurrent validity (Sackett *et al.*, 2007); and predictive validity (Messick, 1955).

In this paper, we discuss the validity of the instrument used to collect data. Specifically, the paper evaluates various response scales used in written survey to collect data in field research. We assert that if the instrument is not accurate, the data, analysis and conclusion would also be inaccurate. An instrument that produces inaccurate result is not a reliable instrument.

2.2 Reliability of an instrument

Reliability is the measure of consistency (Davidhofer *et al.*, 2005). They are various methods used for testing reliability; for instance, Kuder-Richardson formula (Cotina, 1993), Cronbach's alpha (Ritter, 2010) or Spearman-Brown (Eisiga *et al.*, 2012). In this prior literature, the reliability test focuses on the results of the survey. This approach may not be accurate measure for reliability.

Two questions about reliability must be answered: (i) how is consistency of result and reliable instrument different? and (ii) what is the indicator for reliable instrument? Consistency refers to the similarity or uniformity or lack of significant difference in repeated measurements. Consistency of result refers to the uniformity of the result of the survey. A survey may be inaccurate in measuring the construct yet can solicit consistent erroneous result among respondents. For example, a measuring scale that uses to determine the weight of an object may consistently produce the same or similar reading; however, if the scale is defective, the consistently erroneous results would not make the scale a good scale. In terms of reliability, it could only be said that the weight scale consistently produces wrong reading or it is reliably erroneous. Similarly, for the survey used to solicit responses from respondents, if the survey is poor, it is no different than the defective weight scale in the example. Reliability must be examined with Validity.

Validity is the measure of accuracy. In the weight scale example, the scale is reliable in giving the wrong reading. In terms of accuracy it is, the wrong reading makes it fail in validity test due to the lack of accuracy. In the response scale of the survey, validity test is verified to minimal error by which the random values created by the response scale filled the unit circle in the probability space.

An accurate instrument may produce consistently inaccurate result. If reliability is the focus of the test, that reliability would not be accurate for purposes of instrument testing because even with consistently wrong answer, the indication for reliability would have been high, i.e. highly reliable, but wrong answers. For this reason, we assert that an instrument failing validity test also fails reliability test. A reliable instrument is one that could produce accurate result and such result shows consistency in repeated measurements. In this paper, we propose a test for instrument reliability.

3.0 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data obtained through scale components and Monte Carlo simulation

Each data scale provides a range of values. Possible responses in a quantitative survey fall within this range. The descriptive and inferential statistics are provided in Table 1. The term \bar{X} is the mean value of the actual scale and μ represents the expected value of the scale.

Table 1. Descriptive and inferential statistics of survey response scale

Scale	Type	\bar{X}	SD	μ	σ
(0,1,2,3)	Non-Likert	1.50	1.29	0.44	1.29
(1,2,3,4,5)	Likert	3.00	1.58	1.84	1.58
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	Likert	4.00	2.16	2.66	2.16
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	Likert	5.50	3.03	3.93	3.03

Following a Monte Carlo simulation, for each scale type, we use the minimum and maximum values in the scale as the range and calculated how many repetition must there be in order for the probability of each point of measurement to produce normal distribution at 99.98% confidence level. This requirement is achieved by:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow R} \Pr \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \xi - \mu \right\} \leq 0.998 \quad (10)$$

In a random variable set of values $\{X_i\}$, where there are minimum and maximum values, the error of the Monte Carlo is given by:

$$\varepsilon = \left(\frac{\max - \min}{2} \right) / 50 \quad (11)$$

The number of repeat tests needed for the Monte Carlo simulation is determined by:

$$N = \left(\frac{3\sigma_{xi}}{\varepsilon} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

where σ_{xi} is the estimated standard deviation of three values: $X_1 = \max$, $X_2 = \min$, and $X_3 = (\max - \min) / 2$. The expected mean is determined by: $\mu = \bar{X} - S(T(S/\sqrt{n}))$.

Table 2. Skew and kurtosis of response scale

Scale	Type	Skewness	Kurtosis	Monte Carlo*
(0,1,2,3)	Non-Likert	0.00	1.20	22,228.10
(1,2,3,4,5)	Likert	0.00	1.20	24,080.44

(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	Likert	0.00	1.20	23,051.36
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	Likert	0.00	1.20	22,593.99

*The Monte Carlo N repetition for 6-sigma is 23,413.60.

3.2 Procedures for scale accuracy evaluation

We employed three steps to verify the accuracy of the scale in the group of scales: (0,1,2,3), (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10). Step 1 involves the construction of the linear equation for each scale. Step 2 defines the fitness of each scale by using the ratio of the shape and height created by the scale inside the probability space of a unit circle. Step 3 evaluates the accuracy of each scale in the groups of scales though the absolute error of the fitness CDF. These three steps are explained in detailed below.

Step 1. Construct linear equation for the scale. Each scale is converted into a QQ plot and a linear equation in a form of $Y = a + bX$ is obtained through the following process:

$$F(t) = \frac{i - 0.3}{n + 0.4} \quad (13)$$

$$X = \ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - F(t)}\right) \quad (14)$$

$$Y = \ln(\text{scale}) \quad (15)$$

$$I = n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y \quad (16)$$

$$II = n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2 \quad (17)$$

$$b = \frac{I}{II} \quad (18)$$

$$a = \bar{Y} - b\bar{X} \quad (19)$$

Step 2. Define the fitness of the scale. Use the ratio of the shape and height of the expected value of the scale to define the fitness of the response points.

$$Fit = \frac{\beta}{\exp(a)} \quad (20)$$

where β is the shape of the distribution of the scale components obtained by $\beta = 1/b$ and $\exp(a)$ is the scale or the height of the response scale.

Step 3. Determine the error of fitness CDF. Evaluate each scale as a member of a group of various scale to determine which scale type has the most fit using 1.00 of the unit circle as the threshold value. The absolute error of the CDF of the individual scale compared to the center of the probability space in the unit circle determines the accuracy or validity of the scale. Larger the error produces lower accuracy, and lower error produces higher validity indication. Given various scale to be evaluated: $s_i : (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_3)$ has individual fitness: $Fit = \beta / \exp(a)$ compared to the total probability in the unit circle 1.00, individual difference of fitness is obtained as $d_i = Fit - 1$. The CDF of each d_i is determined and compared to the center of the circle or $F(0) = 0.50$. The

absolute value of the error defines the accuracy of the scale: $|E| = \Phi(\text{fit}) - 0.50$. The most accurate response scale is determined on the basis of lowest percentage error or $\% \text{ error} = 1 - |E|$.

3.3 Goodness-of-fit testing to evaluate scales and cross validating the proposed scale accuracy evaluation method

The focus of our evaluation is the instrument used to obtain the data, not the data obtained by the instrument. The evaluation of reliability or validity the literature looked at the responses, not the instrument. In keeping with conventional testing for validity or test for precision, we employed the following fitness tests as part of the cross validation against our proposed simplified version of fitness indicator. The goodness-of-fit (GOF) testing methods presented in this paper include: (i) Cramer-Rao lower bound test, (ii) likelihood ratio test, (iii) Wald statistic, and (iv) Langrange multiplier test. The rationale for using various GOF tests is to determine the accuracy of each scale. The application of the Monte Carlo simulation, couple with NK landscape simulation method allowed us to test for the consistency of the scale.

3.3.1 Cramer-Rao Lower Bound Test

The Cramer-Rao Low Bound test is used to verify the efficiency of thE Likert and non-Likert scales. Efficiency is defined as the optimality of the scale, i.e. experimental design (Everitt, 2002) or hypothesis testing procedure (Nikulin, 2001). More efficient procedure needs less observation, i.e. if the model is efficient, the required response choices should be less. The efficiency of an unbiased estimator, T , for parameter θ is defined as:

$$e(T) = \frac{1 / I(\theta)}{\text{var}(T)} \quad (21)$$

where $I(\theta)$ is the Fisher information of the sample and $e(T)$ is the minimum possible variance of an unbiased estimator divide by its actual variance (Fisher, 1921).

The Cramer-Rao bound is used to prove that $e(T) \leq 1$. Efficiency is achieved at $e(T) = 1$. This is proved by the Cramer-Rao inequality for θ . The Cramer-Rao bound is given by:

$$\text{var}(\hat{\theta}) \geq \frac{1}{I(\theta)} = \frac{1}{-E \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \log f(X | \theta) \right]} \quad (22)$$

Note that for the Fisher information of $X \rightarrow N(\mu, \sigma^2)$, the solution for $-\infty < X < \infty$ is:

$$I(x | \mu) = \log f(x | \mu) = -\frac{1}{2} \log(2\pi\sigma^2) - \frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2} \quad (23)$$

The first and second derivatives are found by: $I'(x | \mu) = \frac{(x - \mu)}{\sigma^2}$ and $I''(x | \mu) = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$. In summary, the Fisher information is simply reduced to:

$$I(\mu) = -E[I''(x | \mu)] = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \text{ which is the inverse of the expected variance: } \sigma^2.$$

3.3.2 Likelihood Ratio Test

The likelihood ratio test is based on chi square distribution with degree of freedom of $df = df_2 - df_1$ (Huelbeck, 1997). The ratio calculation is the likelihood of the null divided by the likelihood of the proposed model. The test statistic was given by as $\Lambda(x)$ by Wilk (1938) as:

$$\Lambda(x) = \frac{L(\theta_0 | X)}{L(\theta_1 | X)} \tag{24}$$

or equivalently:

$$\Lambda(x) = \frac{L(\theta_0 | X)}{\sup\{L(\theta | X) : \theta \in \{\theta_0, \theta_1\}\}} \tag{25}$$

where $L(\theta | X)$ is likelihood function, *sup* is the supremum function. The decision rule is governed by if $\Lambda > c$ do not reject the null hypothesis and if $\Lambda < c$ then reject the null hypothesis. The rejection point is the probability $\Lambda = c$. The variable c and q are selected at specified alpha (error) level whose relationship may be summarized as: $qP(\Lambda = c | H_0) + P(\Lambda < c | H_0) = \alpha$. The likelihood ratio test is a tool against Type I error. Type I error occurs when the null hypothesis is wrongly rejected. In the seminal literature, the likelihood ratio test has been classified as a power test (Neyman & Pearson, 1933). Casella and Berger (2011) wrote (10) and (11) as:

$$\Lambda(x) = \frac{\sup\{L(\theta | x) : \theta \in \theta_0\}}{\sup\{L(\theta | x) : \theta \in \theta\}} \tag{26}$$

Equations (23), (24) and (25) yield the same result.

3.3.2 Wald Statistic

The third test to assess the likelihood function is the Wald statistic. For a single-parameter scenario, the Wald statistic is given by:

$$W = \frac{(\hat{\theta} - \theta_0)^2}{\text{var}(\hat{\theta})} \tag{27}$$

This test is compared to the chi square in case where the data distribution is not normal. In case where the data is normally distributed, the Wald test is given by:

$$W_N = \frac{\hat{\theta} - \theta_0}{\text{se}(\hat{\theta})} \tag{28}$$

where *se* is the standard error of the MLE estimate which is given by:

$$\text{se} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{I_n(MLE)}} \tag{29}$$

where I_n is the Fisher information (Harell, 2001, Fears *et. al.*, 1996, Engle, 1983, and Agresti, 2002).

3.3.4 Lagrange Multiplier (Score Statistic)

The Lagrange multiplier test is also called the score test. The score test had been explained by several authors, such as Bera (2001), Lehman and Casella (1998), Engle (1983), and Cook and Demets (2007). The score test is more appropriate where the deviation between $\hat{\theta}$ and θ is small; this is the case of the adjusted log likelihood proposed by this paper. The score test is given by:

$$U(\theta) = \frac{\partial \log L(\theta | X)}{\partial \theta} \quad (30)$$

The null hypothesis is $\theta = \theta_0$. If the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, the data is treated as chi square distribution. The test statistic is given by:

$$S(\theta_0) = \frac{U(\theta_0)^2}{I(\theta_0)} \quad (31)$$

where $I(\theta_0)$ is the Fisher information or $I(\theta_0) = -E \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} \log L(X | \theta) | \theta \right]$. For normally distributed data, the score test is given by:

$$S^*(\theta) = \sqrt{S(\theta)} \quad (32)$$

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Fitness ratio for scale validity

Following our proposed procedure in step 1, a linear equation for each type of scale was obtained through the QQ plot method where the time function, F(t) was used to construct the linear equation. Table 1 present the linear equation and their respective critical value. The T value is the critical T for the correlation coefficient between X and Y:

$$T_r = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \quad (33)$$

The critical T value is then converted into its Z equivalent in the unit normal distribution table by:

$$Z = ((1.15 * T) - 1.64) + 1.40 \quad (34)$$

With known Z, the percentage probability is obtained by:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{\pi}(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z))} \quad (35)$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$ and $\beta_3 = 0.9000000$.

A linear equation for each scale type may be constructed through the time function. The rationale for using the time function is that, the elements of the scale is presented in sequence. The respondent examines each element in time sequence. For instance, in a scale (0,1,2,3), the

respondents reads the answer code that 0 = none, 1 = low, 2 = medium, and 3 = high. As the respondent selects the response from the sequence, the mental process follows the sequence in time basis. The linear equation, its statistical test for correlation coefficient, and significance level are presented in Table 1. At this preliminary stage of the examination, there is no apparent difference among the scales. All scale has its own linear equation and significance level.

Table 3. Linear equation and significance test for each scale type

Scale type	Linear equation	T	Z	F(Z)	pValue*
(0,1,2,3)	$Y = -1.63 + 1.83X$	3.36	3.62	0.9999	0.0001
(1,2,3,4,5)	$Y = -1.83 + 1.01X$	2.95	3.15	0.9995	0.0005
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	$Y = -1.81 + 0.94X$	3.38	3.65	1.0000	0.0000
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	$Y = -1.79 + 0.88X$	3.92	4.27	1.0000	0.0000

*pValue = $1 - F(Z)$

In the second step, the intercept and slope of the linear equation derived in Table 3 was used to obtain the fit ratio. In this paper, we use the shape and height of the response scale to determine the fit ratio. The shape of the data distribution is obtained by $\beta = 1/b$ and the height of the response is $\eta = \exp(a)$. The fit ratio is obtained by dividing the shape by the height: $fit = \beta/\eta$. The result may be greater than one; we took the natural log of the result to bring the fit ratio nearest to 1.00 as a reference level of the unit circle for the probability space. The value nearest to 1.00 or with the least error compared to the unit circle is considered the best fit. This process is illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4. Fitness ratio for response scale

Scale type	$\beta = 1/b$	$\eta = \exp(a)$	Fitness ratio	LN(fit)	Over flow
(0,1,2,3)	0.55	0.19	2.81	1.03	0.03
(1,2,3,4,5)	0.94	0.16	6.20	1.82	0.82
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	1.07	0.16	6.52	1.88	0.88
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	1.14	0.17	6.81	1.92	0.92

The last step in evaluating which type of scale is the most accurate in capturing scaled responses in the probability space. Tables 3 and 4 illustrate this last procedure. The LN(fit) is compared to the threshold of 1.00 of the unit circle; the difference between the observed LN(fit) and 1.00 is d_i from which the standard score (Z) may be calculated to determine error level (d_i) (Table 3). Note that d_i is the overflow of the fit ratio descaled to fit into the unit circle of 1.00

Table 5. Scale evaluation on fitness indication

Scale type	LN(fit)	Threshold	d_i	Z	F(Z)	pValue
(0,1,2,3)	1.03	1.00	0.03	-0.36	0.3603	0.64
(1,2,3,4,5)	1.82	1.00	0.82	0.59	0.7225	0.28
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	1.88	1.00	0.88	0.66	0.7462	0.25
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	1.92	1.00	0.92	0.71	0.7613	0.24

In table 5, the error's statistics are used to measure how far away are the errors from the center of the unit distribution center ($Z = 0$). The selection of the scale is guided by the absolute error level. Since the error level is calculated by the distance of how large is the difference between the observed and the center of the circle, the scale type with the lowest error level indicates the most precise scale. In table 6 the scale (0,1,2,3) is found to be the best scale.

Table 6. Scale selection on basis of accuracy in measurement

Scale type	F(Z)	F(0)	E	% error	Accuracy
(0,1,2,3)	0.3603	0.5000	0.86	0.1400	Good
(1,2,3,4,5)	0.7225	0.5000	0.09	0.9100	Poor
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	0.7462	0.5000	0.16	0.8400	Poor
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	0.7613	0.5000	0.21	0.7900	Poor

|E| = F(Z) – F(Z). The percentage error is determined by: % error = 1 - |E|.

Survey or written questionnaires with quantitative scale is commonly used. Therefore, selecting the most accurate response scale type becomes important. In accurate scale may lead to inaccurate data and wrong conclusion. Among the four types of scale that we examined, we can categorize the scales into two types: one containing zero and the other not containing zero. Scales without zero could only allow researchers to analyze and test the data under continuous probability. A scale containing zero allows the researcher to test the data under both discrete and continuous probability. Among the four scale types examined by this paper, the response set (0,1,2,3) allows both discrete and continuous probability testing.

4.2 Result of goodness-of-fit (GOF) testing

The results of GOF testing show that the non-Likert scale (0,1,2,3) is the most accurate using the 1.0 area of the unit circle as the reference probability space. While in the Cramer-Rao, the results for Likert and non-Likert scales were consistently score at 1.0. We reject the Cramer-Rao test as inconclusive. The remaining tests of goodness-of-fit: Likelihood ratio, Wald statistic, and Langrange multiplier, show that the non-Likert scale (0,1,2,3) has the best fit in the unit circle's probability space.

Table 7. Test for accuracy by various GOF methods

Scale	Cramer-Rao	Likelihood	Wald	Langrange
(0,1,2,3)	1.00	0.71	0.68	0.70
(1,2,3,4,5)	1.00	0.39	0.54	1.24
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7)	1.00	0.34	0.38	1.76
(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10)	1.00	0.29	0.27	2.56

Note: The maximum value for GOF is 1.00. Note that the Likert scales: (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7) and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10) are outside of the probability space of a unit circle.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This paper evaluated two categories of response scales used in quantitative surveys. The two survey types were Likert and non-Likert. The Likert type included: (1,2,3,4,5), (1,2,3,4,5,6,7), and (1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10). The non-Likert scale type was (0,1,2,3). Reliability and validity were used as indicators to guide efficient scales. Reliability was defined as consistency in the result of the measurement. Validity was defined as the precision of the proposed scale. Efficiency was defined as minimal loss of information. Information loss was measured by $1 - I(\theta)$. We found that the non-Likert scale in a form of (0,1,2,3) were the most robust type. This finding helps to underscore practical tool for instrument calibration. We iterate the erroneous application of the Cronbach's alpha as a tool to measure reliability; the Cronbach's alpha measures the consistency of the responses created by a survey. However, it is not a tool to evaluate the robustness of the instrument. This paper proposed a method of evaluating the robustness of the quantitative scale as a direct and empirical means to assess the efficacy of the instrument, and, thus, serves as a practical tool for instrument calibration. A defective instrument creates defective data; any conclusion drawn from such data fails to meet scientific empiricism. A well calibrated instrument, on the other hand, renders the data free from defect; a conclusion made from such data is more credible.

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